

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Sheath blight (ShB) resistance in wild rices

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Development of host resistance to ShB, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, has been hampered by limited sources of resistance

in existing rice cultivars. To identify additional sources, we tested 76 wild rice accessions in IRRI's ShB nursery. (Some accessions were represented by more than one source, giving a total of 106 entries.)

Seedlings were planted in two 50-cm rows at 5 hills/row, spaced 10 cm between hills and 20 cm between rows. Inoculum (a 10- to 14-d-old culture of

R. solani in a rice hull and grain medium (3:1 vol/vol) was placed between the tillers at the base of each plant 45 and 65 d after seeding. Disease reaction was scored 15-20 d after flowering and relative lesion height (RLH = lesion height [cm]/plant height [cm] x 100) computed.

Although all entries showed ShB symptoms on the leaf sheath, about one-third (35 entries) were more resistant than susceptible check IR58 (see table). On the basis of RLH, *O. minuta* Acc. 101089 (RLH = 18.7%) and *O. rufipogon* Acc. 100907 (RLH = 19.5%) were resistant; 34 other entries were moderately resistant. These accessions may be useful donors of ShB resistance for rice improvement. ■

Wild rices with resistance or moderate resistance to the ShB pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani*. IRRI, 1990.

Species IRGC accession no.	Plants tested (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Lesion height (cm)	RLH*	Grade ^b
<i>O. nivara</i>					
103422	3	127.8	39.4	30.2*	3
103835	3	119.6	36.4	30.1*	3
103840	3	126.7	36.3	29.3	3
101971	1	130.1	38.6	29.3	3
104444	1	113.9	34.1	29.3	3
104473	2	120.2	35.0	28.7*	3
101193	1	100.7	26.6	27.4*	3
103841	3	114.0	31.4	27.3**	3
103841	1	122.1	33.6	27.2*	3
103824	1	91.2	25.2	26.8*	3
104705	1	108.0	28.9	26.5	3
101967	1	120.4	32.2	26.5	3
101973	1	124.2	31.0	25.0*	3
100898	1	101.0	23.6	22.8**	3
<i>O. barthii</i>					
101827	3	88.0	26.0	29.5	3
104304a	2	92.1	23.8	25.3*	3
104304a	1	95.2	22.5	23.0*	3
104304b	1	99.0	22.3	22.0**	3
101317	3	98.6	22.0	21.7**	3
<i>O. perennis</i>					
104765	2	172.3	34.8	30.0	3
104822	2	109.8	31.8	28.3*	3
104796	2	115.3	32.4	27.8*	3
100969	1	135.1	37.4	27.8*	3
103848	1	106.5	29.4	27.6	3
100692	2	107.8	28.5	26.2*	3
104754	2	93.4	24.5	26.0*	3
104782	1	130.0	34.0	25.8*	3
104766a	3	124.9	31.6	24.4**	3
104642	2	86.2	19.3	23.4*	3
104822	1	104.4	24.4	23.0*	3
<i>O. rufipogon</i>					
100907	1	120.8	26.8	21.5*	3
100907	2	154.7	31.0	19.5*	1
<i>O. latifolia</i>					
100966	1	127.8	30.6	23.5*	3
100964	1	122.0	33.0	26.5	3
<i>O. minuta</i>					
101089	1	93.2	17.9	18.7**	1
IR58 (susceptible check)		77.7	32.0	41.2	5

* and ** = significantly different from susceptible check at 5% and 1% level by LSD test. *1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible.

Panicle and grain characters of some glaberrima cultivars in Sierra Leone

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A large number of subsistence farmers in Sierra Leone cultivate *Oryza glaberrima* because of its wide adaptability to stress, high weed competitiveness, and good eating qualities.

Evaluation of cultivars collected during the last 3 yr indicates considerable phenotypic variation.

We evaluated 60 *O. glaberrima* varieties collected in Jan 1988 from upland fields in the Southern Province for variations in morphological and agronomic characters.

Panicle exertion tended to be moderate, panicle type open, and secondary branching rare (Table 1). Threshability was easy (this is a major defect in glaberrimas).

Panicle length, grain length, and grain shape varied widely (Table 2). Panicles 25 cm and longer occurred in Accessions 5886 (Pa China), 5568 (Pa